

Supercritical CO₂ extraction of α -/ β -amyrin from uvaia (*Eugenia pyriformis* Cambess.): Effects of pressure and co-solvent addition

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1 **Supercritical CO₂ extraction of α -/ β -amyrin from uvaia (*Eugenia pyriformis***
2 **Cambess.): Effects of pressure and co-solvent addition**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 The obtaining of α -/ β -amyrin from *Eugenia pyriformis* leaves is a subject with few
18 studies that needs to be explored further in order to extend the understanding about
19 processes to recover these compounds. Thus, the objective of this study was to evaluate
20 the effects of pressure and co-solvent addition in the supercritical CO₂ extraction
21 regarding the global extraction yield, α -/ β -amyrin purity and yield, and antioxidant
22 activity. Extractions were performed at pressures varying in the range 15–30 MPa at fixed
23 temperature of 60 °C. The effect of co-solvent was evaluated at 5 and 15% (w/w) of ethyl
24 acetate and ethanol. The best pressure for increasing α -/ β -amyrin yield was 20 MPa. The
25 co-solvent addition increased the global extraction and α -/ β -amyrin yields, achieving a
26 yield of 16.12 mg g⁻¹ RM (raw material) by using 15% ethanol, while the highest α -/ β -
27 amyryn purity was obtained by using 5% of ethyl acetate as co-solvent.

28 **Keywords:** *Eugenia pyriformis* Cambess; Supercritical fluid extraction; Co-solvent; α -
29 Amyrin; β -Amyrin.

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 In recent years the search for new bioactive compounds with potential applications in the
33 food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries has increased.
34 Nowadays, nutraceutical and cosmetic companies have focused their research on
35 molecules from natural sources [1]. A potential source of bioactive compounds is uvaia,
36 whose extract from the leaves shows high levels of α -amyrin and β -amyrin [2].

37 Uvaia (*Eugenia pyriformis* Cambess.) belongs to the Myrtaceae family, which is one of
38 the most important plant families in Brazil, native from the Atlantic Forest occurring
39 along its extension in the South, Southeast and Northeast of Brazil. Uvaia trees have
40 medium size (6–13 m) [3] and their fruits present orange or yellow fleshy pulp, with
41 acidic flavor and is very aromatic [4]. The fruits of uvaia present high levels of vitamin
42 C, phenolic compounds and carotenoids [5].

43 The main compounds present in uvaia leaves extracts are the isomers α -amyrin and β -
44 amyryn [2]. These compounds are pentacyclic triterpenoids [6] with several bioactive
45 potentials, such as: induction of angiogenesis in vascular endothelial cells [7], anti-
46 Parkinsonian effect [8], anti-inflammatory and anti-fibrogenic
47 [9], antihyperglycemic and hypolipidemic [10], antipruritic [11], anti-inflammatory
48 [[12], [13], [14]], antinociceptive [14], and modulatory potential against
49 hepatic oxidative stress [15].

50 Several extraction techniques can be used to obtain bioactive compounds from plant
51 sources, however, the supercritical CO₂ (scCO₂) extraction stands out for sustainability
52 and safety [16]. scCO₂ is the most commonly used solvent due to its properties such non-
53 flammable, non-toxic, non-corrosive and easy to handle [17,18]. However, scCO₂ has low
54 polarity and therefore has limited ability to extract polar compounds. This limitation can
55 be overcome by adding co-solvent with higher polarity, which can improve the solvent
56 power of CO₂ and increase the extraction yield [19].

57 Considering that the use of co-solvent in the extraction of α -/ β -amyrin from uvaia has
58 been not studied yet, the aim of this work was to evaluate the effects of the addition of
59 two different co-solvents (ethyl acetate and ethanol) and operational pressure of the
60 scCO₂ extraction process. The process was evaluated regarding the total extraction yield
61 and the α -/ β -amyrin yield. In addition, the antioxidant activity of the extracts and the
62 kinetic behavior of the extraction were also investigated.

63 **2. Materials and methods**

64 **2.1. Sample preparation and characterization**

65 The uvaia leaves were collected in a rural property located in Marechal Cândido Rondon,
66 Paraná, Brazil. The leaves were dried in a drying oven with forced air circulation
67 (MA035/2, Marconi, Piracicaba, Brazil) at 40 °C for 48 h. After drying, the leaves were
68 ground in a blender (Philips RI2134, Varginha, MG, Brazil) and classified according to

69 size using a system of Tyler sieve series (16–48 mesh). Particles from 20 mesh (850 μm)
70 to 48 mesh (300 μm) were used in the experiments.

71 The crushed uvaia leaves, called as raw material (RM), were characterized according to
72 moisture (method 920.151), ash (method 923.03) and proteins (method 970.22) [20]. The
73 density of RM was measured using a helium gas pycnometer (Accupyc 1330,
74 Micrometrics, Norcross, USA), and the particle size (D[4;3]) was determined by laser
75 diffraction with a Aero S dry powder disperser (Mastersizer 2000 Malvern Instruments
76 Ltd., Worcestershire, UK).

77 **2.2. Supercritical CO₂ extraction**

78 The extraction process with and without co-solvent was performed in a commercial
79 laboratory scale supercritical fluid extraction unit (MV-10 ASFE System, Waters,
80 Milford, MA, USA). The MV-10 ASFE System was used with 25 mL extraction vessel
81 operating in a semi-automated mode. The extraction vessel was filled with approximately
82 11.3 ± 0.3 g of RM. The system was then heated and pressurized to the desired conditions
83 and thereafter maintained at a static period of 15 min. The solvent flow rate was set at
84 2.0 g min^{-1} and the solvent (S) to feed (F) ratio was kept constant at $S/F = 26$. Initially,
85 the effect of different pressures (15, 20, 25 and 30 MPa) was studied at a constant
86 temperature of $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which was selected considering the results found in a previous
87 study [2]. The evaluation of the use of co-solvent was performed using two different
88 solvents, ethanol (EtOH) and ethyl acetate (EtAc), at concentrations of 5 and 15% (w/w).
89 After extraction, the solvents were removed from the extracts using a drying oven at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
90 for 24 h. The total extraction yields were calculated as the ratio between the extracted
91 mass and the amount of RM used on a dry basis. All extractions were performed in
92 duplicate.

93 **2.2.1. Extraction kinetics**

94 Kinetic experiments were also performed in the MV-10 ASFE System equipped with the
95 25 mL vessel, keeping the extraction conditions at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 20 MPa, and using the
96 following solvents: only scCO_2 and scCO_2 +5% EtAc. The solvent flow rate was kept at
97 2 g min^{-1} for 220 min to ensure that the diffusion-controlled period was reached in the
98 overall extraction curve (OEC). Extracts were collected at 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80,
99 100, 130, 160, 190 and 220 min.

100 **2.3. Extracts analyses**

101 **2.3.1. Quantification of α -amyirin and β -amyirin**

102 The contents of α -amyirin and β -amyirin were determined using an HPLC-DAD (Alliance
103 E2695, Waters, Milford, MA, USA) according to the method described by Hernández-
104 Vázquez et al. [21]: the separation was carried out isocratically using a Phenomenex
105 Kinetex C18 column ($4.6 \text{ mm} \times 250 \text{ mm}$, $5 \mu\text{m}$) and methanol as the mobile phase for
106 15 min. The temperature was $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the flow rate was 0.9 mL min^{-1} . The samples
107 (0.2 mg mL^{-1} in isopropyl alcohol) were analyzed at 210 nm. The α -amyirin and β -amyirin

108 standard solutions (0.01-0.20 mg mL⁻¹ in isopropyl alcohol) were used to obtain
109 the calibration curves, which showed regressions of R² > 0.99. The regression equations
110 for calibrations curves are y = 3423.7x for α-amyrin and y = 4552.3x for β-amyrin.

111 **2.3.2. Antioxidant activity and total phenolic content**

112 A screening for antioxidant activity was performed according to Tepe et al. [22] with
113 some modifications. Five microliters of solutions prepared in isopropyl
114 alcohol (2 mg mL⁻¹) of each extract were applied on thin layer chromatography (TLC)
115 plates (TLC Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Hexane-ethyl acetate (8:2,
116 v/v) mixture was used as developer. After development, plates were dried and sprayed
117 with a 0.2% (m/v) DPPH solution in ethanol and then left for 30 min at room
118 temperature (25 ± 2 °C). After this time, the plates were observed; yellow spots formed
119 from bleaching of the purple color of DPPH indicate positive antioxidant activity.

120 Extracts with positive antioxidant activity were analyzed according to Enujiugha et al.
121 [23], 0.2 mL of the extract solution (2 mg mL⁻¹) in ethanol was added to 3.8 mL DPPH
122 solution (0.1 mM in ethanol) and left in dark at room temperature for 30 min. Then, the
123 absorbance was measured at 517 nm (LAMBDA 35 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer,
124 PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). Ethanol was used as blank and the negative control
125 was prepared by mixing 3.8 mL of DPPH solution with 0.2 mL of ethanol. The analyses
126 were performed in triplicate and the results were expressed as micromoles
127 of Trolox equivalent per gram of extract (µM T/g).

128 The total phenolics content (TPC) in uvaia extracts was determined using the Folin-
129 Ciocalteu method as described by Santos et al. [24]. The extract was dissolved in ethanol
130 (2.0 mg mL⁻¹), 0.3 mL of this solution was mixed with 2.5 mL of aqueous solution of
131 Folin-Ciocalteu reagent at 10% (v/v) and 2.0 mL of sodium carbonate at 7.5%. After 2 h
132 at ambient temperature, the absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer
133 (LAMBDA 35 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer, PerkinElmer) at 760 nm. The results were
134 expressed in mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per g of extract (mg GEA g⁻¹). The
135 analyses were performed in triplicate.

136 **2.4. Statistical analysis**

137 Results were expressed as mean values ± standard deviation (SD). The software
138 Statistica® version 7.0 (StatSoft, Tulsa, OK, USA) was used to perform the analysis of
139 variance (ANOVA) test and the significant differences were evaluated by Tukey's test at
140 5% significance level.

141 **3. Results and discussion**

142 **3.1. Raw material characterization**

143 The raw material characterization demonstrated that it contains 4.7 ± 0.4% moisture,
144 10.60 ± 0.04% ash, and 11.8 ± 0.3% proteins. The mean particle diameter was 672 ± 9 µm

145 and the true density was $1404.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. No results were found in the literature
146 related to the proximate composition of uvaia leaves.

147 **3.2. Effect of pressure on supercritical CO₂ extraction**

148 The global extraction yields obtained at 60 °C and pressures between 15 and 30 MPa
149 ranged from 1.08 ± 0.01 to $2.04 \pm 0.01 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ raw material (RM) (Fig. 1),
150 corroborating those results reported in the literature [2], where a extraction yield of 1.69 g
151 100 g^{-1} RM was verified for the extract from uvaia leaves at 60 °C and 20 MPa. It can be
152 seen that the pressure increase had a positive effect on the total extraction yield, since it
153 was possible to double the yield at 30 MPa in comparison with the value obtained at
154 15 MPa.

155 Table 1 shows the results of α -amyrin and β -amyrin content in the extracts, which means
156 the α -/ β -amyrin purity, and the yield of these compounds, expressed as $\text{g } \alpha$ -/ β -amyrin per
157 g of RM. The α -/ β -amyrin content in the extracts ranged from 43.5 ± 0.8 to $60 \pm 1 \text{ g}$
158 100 g^{-1} extract. The highest values were obtained at 20 and 25 MPa, that did not show
159 statistical difference between each other. The highest yield of α -/ β -amyrin ($8.7 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg}$
160 g^{-1} RM) was obtained at 20 MPa and the result was not statistically different from that
161 the observed at 25 MPa ($8.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg } \text{g}^{-1}$ RM). It is possible to observe in Table 1 that
162 the pressure of 30 MPa reduced drastically the α -/ β -amyrin purity ($43.5 \pm 0.8 \text{ g}$
163 100^{-1} extract) as a result of the co-extraction of other compounds that act as diluting
164 agents for the compounds of interest.

165 In a previous study [2], the α -/ β -amyrin content obtained from uvaia leaves by
166 scCO_2 extraction at 60 °C and 20 MPa was $67 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ extract and the yield of α -/ β -
167 amyrin was $11.4 \text{ mg } \text{g}^{-1}$ RM. This variation may be related to characteristics of the raw
168 material, since the composition of the obtained extracts can vary according to several
169 factors such as: harvest season, mode of collection, storage, and preparation of the raw
170 material [25].

171 β -amyrin was quantified in extracts obtained from dandelion (*Taraxacum officinal*)
172 leaves by scCO_2 extraction (65 °C and 45 MPa) and a yield of $0.0446 \text{ mg } \text{g}^{-1}$ dry RM was
173 reported [26]. Other authors [27] obtained a yield of 1.2 mg of β -amyrin per g^{-1} of
174 common fig (*Ficus carica*) latex obtained by hydrolysis and direct solvent
175 extraction with dichloromethane and n-hexane. In another study, α -amyrin was extracted
176 from hagar (*Commiphora holtziana*) oleo-gum resin extracted with acetone and n-hexane,
177 and 0.2 mg of α -amyrin g^{-1} RM was detected [28]. Dias et al. [29] reported a yield of 3.1
178 and 1.7 mg of α - amyrin and β -amyrin g^{-1} RM, respectively, from Almecegueira
179 (*Protium sp.*) resin obtained by Soxhlet extraction with dichloromethane. Comparing the
180 results obtained in the literature with those obtained in the present study, uvaia leaves
181 stand out as a promising source of α -/ β -amyrin, since it was possible to achieve higher
182 yields of α -amyrin, β -amyrin and α -/ β -amyrin higher than all those results reported in the
183 literature.

184 **3.3. Effect of co-solvent addition on supercritical CO₂ extraction**

185 Based on the results previously presented, the pressure of 20 MPa was selected to be used
186 in the following trials to evaluate the effect of co-solvent addition on the extraction yield,
187 purity and yield of α -/ β -amyrin.

188 The extraction yields obtained with the addition of co-solvent ranged from 2.4 ± 0.1 to
189 3.95 ± 0.01 g 100 g⁻¹ RM, significantly higher than those obtained using only scCO₂ as
190 solvent (1.73 ± 0.01 g 100 g⁻¹ RM) (Fig. 2). The addition of EtOH as co-solvent resulted
191 in higher yields than those obtained by using EtAc. This behavior can be explained by the
192 increase in the solubility of polar compounds in the mixtures scCO₂ + EtOH and scCO₂ +
193 EtAc, compared with its solubility in pure scCO₂ [30].

194 The highest extraction yield (3.95 ± 0.01 g 100 g⁻¹ RM) was obtained by using 15% EtOH
195 as co-solvent. However, when it comes to natural products, the extraction yield is not the
196 only criterion to be considered. The chemical composition of the extracts is of great
197 importance to determine its quality. Table 2 shows the results for purity of α -amyrin and
198 β -amyrin and the yield of these compounds per g of raw material obtained in the
199 scCO₂ extraction with co-solvent addition.

200 Among the extracts obtained with the addition of co-solvent, only the extract obtained
201 with 15% EtOH showed a significant difference in terms of the purity of α -/ β -amyrin in
202 relation to the extraction with pure scCO₂. The α -/ β -amyrin content of the extract obtained
203 with 15% EtOH (41 ± 4 g 100 g⁻¹ extract) was 28% lower than that obtained with pure
204 scCO₂ (57 ± 3 g 100 g⁻¹ extract). The addition of 15% EtOH possibly increased the
205 amount of polar compounds extracted, which explains the decrease in the proportion of
206 α -/ β -amyrin in the extract. Similar result was found by adding 10% EtOH in
207 scCO₂ extraction of common alder (*Alnus glutinosa*), where
208 the triterpenoid lupeol content was reduced in comparison with the extraction with pure
209 CO₂ [31]. Rodrigues et al. [32] also studied the effect of adding EtOH as co-solvent for
210 the artemisia (*Artemisia annua*) extraction and observed a reduction of
211 the artemisinin content with increasing the EtOH amount in the scCO₂. This occurs
212 because the use of co-solvent increase the number of extracted compounds and decrease
213 the extraction selectivity [33].

214 On the other hand, it is possible to observe in Table 2 that the yield of α -/ β -amyrin was
215 increased by adding co-solvent to the scCO₂. The extract obtained with 15% EtOH
216 resulted in the highest α -/ β -amyrin yield. This result is consistent with the literature,
217 where the addition of 15% EtOH as co-solvent for the scCO₂ extraction increased the
218 extraction of naringin from grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*) [34]. However, the use of high
219 amounts of co-solvent in scCO₂ extraction can increase the manufacturing costs. The
220 lower purity of α -/ β -amyrin obtained when 15% EtOH was added may increase the cost
221 of isolation/purification of these compounds in potential industrial application of the
222 process. In addition, EtAc has a lower boiling point than EtOH which facilitates solvent
223 removal from the extract.

224 The addition of 5% EtAc as co-solvent resulted a α -/ β -amyrin purity similar to that
225 obtained with pure scCO₂ and enabled a α -/ β -amyrin yield 31% higher than the yield
226 found using pure scCO₂. Although the α -/ β -amyrin yield obtained with 5% EtAc was
227 lower than that obtained with 15% EtOH, this last condition is not interesting considering
228 the purity reasons already discussed. Considering these results, the addition of 5% EtAc
229 was chosen to evaluate the kinetic behavior of the extracts.

230 3.4. Extraction kinetics

231 Based on the results previously obtained, the kinetic behavior was evaluated using only
232 pure scCO₂ as solvent and with the addition of EtAc at the proportion of 5%. Fig. 3 shows
233 the overall extractions curves (OEC) for the extractions obtained at 60 °C and 20 MPa.
234 From the kinetic curves, it can be observed that the initial extraction rate was increased
235 using scCO₂ + 5% EtAc (Fig. 3). The extraction yields obtained for pure scCO₂, scCO₂ +
236 5% EtAc were 2.3 ± 0.1 and 2.38 ± 0.05 g 100 g⁻¹ RM, respectively, for 220 min of
237 extraction (S/F = 40). In this case, the addition of 5% EtAc did not significantly increase
238 the extraction yield, differently to the results observed for the scCO₂ extraction of candeia
239 (*Eremanthus erythropappus*) that presented a higher extraction yield using 5% EtAc
240 compared with pure scCO₂ [35].

241 The OEC's obtained with pure scCO₂ and scCO₂ + EtAc reached almost the same
242 extraction yield at the diffusional period of the process. It is observed in Fig. 4 that the α -
243 β -amyrin yield (mg α - β -amyrin g⁻¹ RM) reached the diffusional period for all
244 conditions. Also, the previously selected S/F was convenient for the extractions with and
245 without co-solvent considering the values of α - β -amyrin yield because after S/F = 26
246 both OEC's reached a constant value, indicating that the α - β -amyrin extractable under
247 these conditions were nearly exhausted from the raw material. The highest α - β -amyrin
248 purity (57 ± 2 g 100 g⁻¹ extract) obtained in the kinetic study was observed for the OEC
249 with 5% EtAc after a S/F = 18, confirming the results previously obtained.

250 3.5. Antioxidant activity

251 TLC assay for the screening of antioxidant activity using the DPPH demonstrated that
252 just the extract obtained at 60 °C and 20 MPa with the addition of 15% EtOH presented
253 antioxidant activity, probably due to the polarity of the solvent used during the extraction
254 that enable the solubilization of other compounds responsible for the antioxidant activity
255 of the extracts [22,24]. Thus, this extract was the only sample submitted to the
256 quantification of antioxidant potential as Trolox equivalent and the total phenolic content
257 (TPC), resulting 132 ± 2 μ mol TE g⁻¹ extract for DPPH and 29 ± 4 mg GAE g⁻¹ extract
258 for TPC test. No results were found in the literature for antioxidant activity and TPC for
259 extracts of uvaia (*E. pyriformis*) obtained by scCO₂ extraction, but other plants of the
260 same genus have been studied. For the extract obtained from pitanga (*E. uniflora*) leaves
261 the result for TPC was similar using pure CO₂ as solvent, showing 32.7 mg g⁻¹ extract
262 [36]. Antioxidant activity was analyzed for extracts obtained with pure supercritical
263 CO₂ from cerejeira-do-mato (*E. involucrata*) leaves, the extracts obtained at the same
264 temperature and pressure conditions (60 °C and 20 MPa) showed values of 90.50–
265 95.35 μ mol g⁻¹ extract [37].

266 4. Conclusions

267 Extracts from *Eugenia pyriformis* leaves were obtained using pressures between 15 MPa
268 and 30 MPa with pure scCO₂ and the effect of co-solvent addition was also tested by
269 adding 5 and 15% of EtOH and EtAc at 20 MPa and 60 °C. The effects of extraction

270 conditions were evaluated considering the total yield, purity of α -/ β -amyrin and the yield
271 of those compounds per g of raw material.

272 The use of pressures higher than 20 MPa did not improve the α -/ β -amyrin yield. On the
273 other hand, the use of 5% EtAc as co-solvent presented positive effect increasing the α -
274 / β -amyrin yield by 31% compared with pure scCO₂. The results showed that only the
275 extract obtained with 15% EtOH as co-solvent demonstrated antioxidant activity. The
276 results demonstrated that the addition of 5% EtAc to the scCO₂ extraction is a good
277 alternative for obtaining α -/ β -amyrin from uvaia leaves. Further studies regarding on
278 scale-up and economics of the process must be conducted to establish its viability at
279 industrial level.

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416 **Figures:**

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418

419 **Figure 1:** Total extraction yields of the extracts obtained from uvaia leaves by
420 scCO₂ extraction at 60 °C using different pressures at S/F = 26. Different letters indicate
421 significant difference (p < 0.05).

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423

424 **Figure 2:** Total extraction yields of the extracts obtained from uvaia leaves by
425 scCO₂ extraction at 60 °C and 20 MPa using different co-solvent at S/F = 26. Different
426 letters indicate significant difference (p < 0.05).

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430 **Figure 3:** Overall extraction curves of extractions performed at 60 °C and 20 MPa with
431 and without co-solvent addition. ■ pure scCO₂; ▲ scCO₂ + 5% EtAc. Results presented
432 in dry basis (d.b.).

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434

435 **Figure 4:** α-/β-amyrin yield of the extractions performed at 60 °C and 20 MPa with and
436 without co-solvent addition: ■ pure CO₂; ▲ CO₂ + 5% EtAc. Results presented in dry
437 basis (d.b.).

438

439 **Tables:**

440 **Table 1:** Results of α -/ β -amyrin content and α -/ β -amyrin yield of the extracts obtained from
 441 uvaia leaves by scCO₂ extraction at 60 °C using different pressures at S/F = 26.

442

Pressure (MPa)	Purity (g 100 g ⁻¹ extract)			Yield (mg g ⁻¹ RM)		
	α -amyrin	β -amyrin	Total	α -amyrin	β -amyrin	Total
15	7.1 ± 0.6 ^a	47 ± 3 ^b	54 ± 3 ^a	0.8 ± 0.1 ^c	5.1 ± 0.3 ^b	5.9 ± 0.3 ^a
20	6.8 ± 0.6 ^a	50 ± 3 ^{ab}	57 ± 3 ^{ab}	1.2 ± 0.1 ^b	8.7 ± 0.5 ^a	9.9 ± 0.6 ^b
25	6.7 ± 0.3 ^a	52.9 ± 0.7 ^a	60 ± 1 ^b	1.1 ± 0.1 ^{ab}	8.6 ± 0.2 ^a	9.7 ± 0.2 ^{bc}
30	5.0 ± 0.2 ^b	38.5 ± 0.7 ^c	43.5 ± 0.8 ^c	1.02 ± 0.04 ^a	7.8 ± 0.1 ^a	9.0 ± 0.2 ^c

443 Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation (n=4) and different superscript letters in the same
 444 column indicate significant difference at p<0.05.

445

446 **Table 2:** Results of α -/ β -amyrin content and α -/ β -amyrin yield of the extracts obtained
 447 from uvaia leaves by scCO₂ extraction at 60 °C and 20 MPa using co-solvents at S/F = 26.

448

Co-solvent	Purity (g 100 g ⁻¹ extract)			Yield (mg g ⁻¹ RM)		
	α -amyrin	β -amyrin	Total	α -amyrin	β -amyrin	Total
pure CO ₂	6.8 ± 0.6 ^a	50 ± 3 ^{ab}	57 ± 3 ^{ab}	1.2 ± 0.1 ^b	8.7 ± 0.5 ^c	9.9 ± 0.6 ^c
5% EtAc	6.6 ± 0.5 ^{ab}	52 ± 3 ^a	59 ± 4 ^a	1.58 ± 0.07 ^a	12.4 ± 0.4 ^b	13.00 ± 0.5 ^b
15% EtAc	5.7 ± 0.2 ^c	45.7 ± 0.5 ^b	51.4 ± 0.6 ^b	1.6 ± 0.1 ^a	12.5 ± 0.5 ^b	14.1 ± 0.6 ^b
5% EtOH	6.0 ± 0.1 ^{bc}	45.8 ± 0.7 ^b	51.8 ± 0.8 ^b	1.63 ± 0.05 ^a	12.5 ± 0.2 ^b	14.1 ± 0.3 ^b
15% EtOH	4.4 ± 0.4 ^d	37 ± 3 ^c	41 ± 4 ^c	1.7 ± 0.1 ^a	14.4 ± 0.8 ^a	16.1 ± 0.9 ^a

449 Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation (n=4) and different superscript letters in the same
 450 column indicate significant difference at p<0.05.

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